

Erasmus+ Programme

Key Action 2 - Cooperation Partnerships in School Education

DESK RESEARCH COUNTRY REPORT

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Other Countries

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A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

Grant Agreement No. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043

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Short Description	This report presents the findings of desk research conducted in selected non-partner countries: Australia, Belgium, Finland, Rhode Island (USA), Spain, and the United Kingdom. It analyses research evidence, good practices, and regulatory frameworks related to social media use, online safety and media literacy among preadolescents, and identifies key insights to inform the development of the ASAP project.

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
Introduction	7
1. Australia	8
1.1. Statistical data	8
1.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents	9
1.3. Good practice examples	12
1.4. Legislation and regulation	13
1.5. Other sources of support.....	14
1.6. Conclusions.....	14
2. Belgium	17
2.1. Statistical data	17
2.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents	17
2.3. Good practice examples	19
2.4. Legislation and regulation	22
2.5. Conclusions.....	23
3. Finland.....	26
3.1. Statistical data	26
3.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents	27
3.3. Good practice examples	28
3.4. Legislation and regulation	30
3.5. Conclusions.....	31
4. Rhode Island (USA).....	34
4.1. Statistical data	34
4.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents	34
4.3. Good practice examples	36
4.4. Other programs and activities.....	37
4.5. Conclusions.....	39
5. Spain.....	41
5.1. Statistical data	41
5.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents	42
5.3. Good practice examples	43
5.4. Legislation and regulation	44

5.5.	Conclusions.....	45
6.	United Kingdom: NGOs and Legislation Frameworks.....	47
6.1.	Statistical data	47
6.2.	National research on social media and (pre)adolescents	47
6.3.	Good practice examples (national and NGOs)	48
6.4.	UK legislation and regulation	50
6.5.	European Union legislation and regulation.....	50
6.6.	International organisations (United Nations).....	51
6.7.	Conclusions.....	52
	Conclusions	54

Executive Summary

Introduction and objectives

This report presents a comparative analysis of policies, practices, and educational strategies addressing social media use and misuse among preadolescents in selected non-partner countries. It specifically examines interventions designed to prevent and combat cyberbullying, as well as initiatives aimed at enhancing digital and social media literacy. The report contributes to the final desk research deliverable of the ASAP project and offers insights that may inform the development of evidence-based recommendations for schools, policymakers, and relevant stakeholders across partner countries.

The primary objectives is to expand the desk research conducted in five partner countries to selected non-partner countries to: 1) identify good practices and strategies that successfully address cyberbullying and online safety among preadolescents, 2) understand the legislative, policy, and institutional frameworks that support safe social media use in school contexts, 3) examine the role of educational programs, parental guidance, and community engagement in shaping positive digital behaviours, 4) highlight areas of risk, including mental health implications, gender-specific vulnerabilities, and early exposure to online platforms.

Country selection rationale

The selection of non-partner countries was guided by multiple considerations. First, as ASAP is an EU-funded project, it was important to include non-partner EU countries such as Finland, Belgium, and Spain, enabling a comparison within the EU context. Second, the research included well-developed, non-EU countries (Australia, the United States, United Kingdom) that are often recognized for innovative approaches to digital safety and cyberbullying prevention. Third, Scandinavian countries were prioritized due to their advanced school systems and emphasis on holistic education, exemplified by Finland. Finally, practical considerations such as language accessibility and data availability led to the inclusion of Spain.

The resulting countries—Australia, Belgium, Finland, Rhode Island (USA), Spain, and the United Kingdom—represent diverse approaches in terms of policy, school practice, and cultural attitudes toward digital citizenship and online safety. Each country report was structured to present statistical data, national research findings, good practice examples, legislative frameworks, and other relevant resources.

Key findings by country

Australia

Australia demonstrates a high level of institutional commitment to online safety. The establishment of the Office of the eSafety Commissioner in 2015 reflects a structured governmental approach, combining regulatory oversight with education and community outreach. Statistical data indicate that over half of Australian youth experience cyberbullying, with significant prevalence among LGBTQ+ youth and children with disabilities. National surveys highlight that younger students, particularly those in Years 4 and 6, face higher bullying rates than older peers.

Good practices include the Young and eSafe (YES) program, digital citizenship curricula in schools, and professional development opportunities for educators. Legislative frameworks, such as the Enhancing Online Safety Act 2015 and the Criminal Code Amendment Act 2019, complement these initiatives by creating accountability mechanisms for online abuse. Australia’s strength lies in the integration of legal, educational, and community-based measures, providing a comprehensive ecosystem for protecting children online.

Belgium

Belgium presents a highly connected digital environment combined with a decentralised approach to media education and online safety. While national statistical data on children under 13 remain limited, available research indicates early and frequent social media use among preadolescents, alongside exposure to online risks such as cyberbullying, harmful content and social pressure, with girls more frequently reporting emotionally distressing experiences.

Media education is primarily addressed at Community level, in line with the distribution of competences for education and youth policies. Key public actors include Mediawijs in the Flemish Community, the Conseil supérieur de l’éducation aux médias in the French-speaking Community, and the Mediazentrum in the German-speaking Community. These institutions support schools and educators through resources, training and school-based interventions, emphasising critical media literacy as a citizenship competence. In the absence of a dedicated national law, the Belgian case illustrates how decentralised institutional structures can support coherent media education practices.

Finland

Finland exhibits a strong focus on education and preventative measures. Almost all Finnish children aged 12–14 have access to a smartphone, and cyberbullying affects nearly half of youth aged 10–17. National research identifies gender- and age-specific vulnerabilities, with girls more likely to encounter serious cyberbullying.

Good practice initiatives are anchored in the digital literacy curriculum, parental involvement, and the internationally recognized KiVa anti-bullying program, which combines universal education with targeted interventions and annual monitoring. Legislative measures, such as guarantees of broadband access, data protection laws, and school obligations to provide safe environments, underpin these efforts. Finland’s approach emphasizes early intervention, cross-sector collaboration, and long-term monitoring of program effectiveness.

Rhode Island (USA)

In Rhode Island, media literacy education is unevenly implemented across school districts. While digital exposure is high among preadolescents, only a minority receive systematic instruction on analysing media messages, understanding advertising, or addressing online risks. Cyberbullying prevalence is modest compared to national U.S. averages, yet significant gaps in structured prevention and education persist.

Prominent interventions include the Media Education Lab, which provides professional development for educators, community engagement programs, and resources for critical media literacy. State legislation addresses bullying and cyberbullying through six regulatory documents, but media literacy

integration into curricula remains largely dependent on NGOs and local initiatives. Rhode Island illustrates the challenges of translating policy intent into consistent practice at the local level.

Spain

Spain presents a digital environment characterized by high social media penetration and pervasive use among adolescents. Cyberbullying rates are lower than in Australia or Finland, yet there is a clear recognition of risks, including mental health impacts, exposure to harmful content, and the need for parental mediation.

Good practices include the PDA Bullying Platform, Aprender a Mirar Foundation, and initiatives by the National Cybersecurity Center (INCIBE). These programs provide resources for students, parents, and educators and promote reporting mechanisms, digital literacy, and awareness campaigns. Legislative instruments, such as the Law on Comprehensive Protection of Children and Adolescents against Violence (2021) and the Organic Law on Digital Rights (2018), provide a robust framework to protect minors online. Spain's model highlights the combination of legal safeguards, institutional collaboration, and public awareness initiatives.

United Kingdom

In the UK, social media use among preadolescents has increased sharply, with platforms like TikTok, Instagram, and Snapchat dominating daily interactions. Research underscores mental health concerns, including anxiety and loneliness linked to excessive social media use.

Key initiatives include the UK Safer Internet Centre, Childnet International's Digital Citizenship Programme, the Digital Schools Awards, and the Social Media Code of Conduct for Schools. Legislative developments, notably the Online Safety Bill, aim to impose duties on platforms to mitigate harmful content and protect minors. European frameworks, such as GDPR, the Audiovisual Media Services Directive, and the Digital Services Act, further reinforce protections. The UK demonstrates an integrated approach combining legislation, school-based programs, NGO engagement, and public awareness.

Conclusions

The desk research across non-partner countries reveals several convergent themes and critical implications: institutional and policy frameworks, mental health considerations, age and gender-tailored approaches, implementation gaps of translating policy frameworks into consistent local practice, early and unsupervised exposure to social media etc.

The research highlights that effective approaches to online safety combine legislation, education, parental engagement, and community involvement. Cross-country learning and the adaptation of successful practices to local contexts can enhance the resilience and well-being of preadolescents, equipping them with the skills, awareness, and protections necessary to navigate the digital world safely.

Introduction

This report provides context analysis of the existing good practices and strategies for dealing with social media uses and misuses in the school context, educational programmes/activities to prevent and combat cyberbullying and enhance digital/social media literacy among preadolescents in the selected non-partner countries. It serves as an input for the ASAP Final Desk Research Report.

There has been quite a debate among the project partners on which non-partner countries to select for the context analysis. Finally, it has been agreed that different rationales for selection were possible and acceptable. The following rationales have been considered for the selection of non-partner countries:

- As ASAP is an EU-funded project, it is important to focus on the non-partner EU countries (Finland, Spain, Belgium).
- It is important to analyse well-developed non-EU countries, representatives of “the Western world” where it is more likely that advanced practices related to social media and cyberbullying have already been introduced (Australia, Rhode Island, USA, United Kingdom).
- It would be useful to analyse Scandinavian countries, which are well-known for their modern and advanced school system (Finland).
- Due to practical reasons, it would be useful to analyse those non-partner countries with low language barrier and higher possibility to access and retrieve relevant data (Spain).

In the following chapters, the country reports of the selected non-partner countries are listed in alphabetical order: Australia, Belgium, Finland, Rhode Island (USA), Spain, United Kingdom.

Each non-partner country report is similarly structured to provide relevant information on the following topics: 1) statistical data, 2) national research on social media and (pre)adolescents, 3) good practice examples, 4) legislation and regulation, 5) other topics (if relevant) and 6) conclusions.

1. Australia

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1.1. Statistical data

With its population of over 26 million ([Australian Bureau of Statistics](#)) and 5.1 million children, of which 2.2 million are aged between five and 12 years, Australia may not be a leader in addressing online safety and cyberbullying; however, it was one of the first to establish a dedicated agency, the [Office of the eSafety Commissioner](#) (July 2015 under the Enhancing Online Safety Act 2015), to address online safety issues of children and young people experiencing severe cyberbullying. The Commissioner leads, coordinates and advises on online safety issues to ensure all Australians have safe, positive and empowering experiences online. The Office primarily provides three complaints and reporting schemes: Cyber Bullying Complaints Scheme, which investigates cyberbullying severe material; Online Content Scheme, which investigates offensive and illegal online content, mainly child sexual abuse material; and Image-Based Abuse Portal, which investigates reports of image-based abuse.

On the [Australian Bureau of Statistics](#) webpage, there can be found the [Household Use of Information Technology](#) survey conducted in 2016-2017, published in March 2018. 86% of households have internet access, which has remained steady in recent years. It also states that while 97% of households with children aged under 15 have internet access, the number for households without children aged under 15 is only 82%; this seems to be quite a big difference and points out the importance of internet access for the younger generation, due to various reasons. Nearly all (99%) households with children under 15 use a mobile or smartphone to access the internet, which also points out how important it has become such a personal device for pre-adolescents and adolescents. Regarding child protection online indicators, in 2016-17, 14% of connected households with children aged 5-14 stated that a child had been exposed to inappropriate material, and 5% of these households stated that a child aged 5-14 had been subject to cyberbullying.

As per a 2019 survey conducted by Headspace (a former headspace National Youth Mental Health Foundation), 53% of young Australians have encountered cyberbullying. The survey mentions that despite the extensive prevalence of this issue, some children and teenagers choose not to report cyberbullying incidents, allowing them to linger until they either resolve themselves or escalate to an unbearable level. The cyberbullying statistics from Australia (Headspace) on the extent of negative online experiences faced by many young individuals are the following:

- 53% of young Australians have encountered cyberbullying, and more than one in three Australians have experienced online trolling.
- 44% of Australian teenagers have encountered at least one negative online incident.
- 21% of Australian teens have reported instances of online harassment.
- Australian teens spend an average of 14.4 hours online each week.
- 11% of Australian teens have shared a picture of themselves with an online stranger.
- Racial motivation accounts for 17.9 % of cyberbullying cases in Australia.
- LGBTQ+ children are three times more likely to experience online bullying than their peers.

- Students with physical or mental health disabilities experience cyberbullying more frequently than those without disabilities (10% of school students have some form of disability).

According to this study, cyberbullying is a significant issue for children and teenagers in Australia, necessitating an understanding of both the problem and potential solutions from those responsible for their well-being. Although efforts are being made to establish cyberbullying laws, there remains a gap, even as the issue affects half of the country's youth.

1.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

The study on [Australia's Children](#) (last updated in 2022) states that 7 in 10 children aged 12–13 experienced at least one bullying-like behaviour within a year; 1 in 5 Year 4 students (average age 10) experience bullying every week; 1 in 4 children aged 8–12 who completed the eSafety Commissioner's Youth Digital Participation Survey experienced unwanted contact and content while online; almost half (46%) of children aged 12–13 who experienced at least one bullying-like behaviours within a year also used bullying-like behaviours against another child. In the absence of a single comprehensive national data source on children who experience bullying, this section draws on multiple data sources to provide some insight into the topic. (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare 2020. Australia's children. Cat. No. CWS 69. Canberra: AIHW)

The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) is managed by the [Australian Council for Educational Research \(ACER\)](#) and jointly funded by the Australian Government and the state and territory governments. The data of TIMSS 2015 shows that younger students are bullied more than older students, Year 4 students (average age 10) were more likely to have been bullied than Year 8 students (average age 14). About 56% of Year 4 students and 43% of Year 8 students had been bullied monthly or weekly during the school year ([Thomson, Wernert, O'Grady, Rodrigues, 2017](#)).

Figure 1: Proportion of children bullied during the school year, by frequency of bullying, by year level at school, 2015.
Source: TIMSS 2015 (Thomson et al., 2017)

The eSafety Commissioner's **Youth Digital Participation Survey** showed that unwanted contact and content was the most reported negative online experience for children aged 8–12, with 24% of all children experiencing it. Boys and girls had similar rates for all the online negative experiences examined ([Office of the eSafety Commissioner 2018](#)).

Figure 2: Proportion of children aged 8–12 who had negative online experiences by sex, July 2016 to June 2017. Source: Youth Digital Participation Survey, Office of the eSafety Commissioner

[Australian Child Wellbeing Project \(ACWP\)](#) - This study conducted by the Australian Council for Educational Research in 2014 found that 75% of preadolescents aged 8-14 in Australia reported using social media, with Facebook and YouTube being the most popular platforms. The study also found that preadolescents who spent more time on social media reported lower levels of well-being, including lower levels of satisfaction with their life and lower levels of positive emotions. It worked with a sample of students in Years 4 (age 10), 6 (age 12) and 8 (age 14) and was completed during Term 3 2014 in 180 schools across Australia. More than 5,400 students participated in the survey, which collected valuable information on various aspects of young people’s wellbeing. It has shown, for example, that more children with disabilities experienced bullying-like behaviours in the same school term the survey was conducted than children without disabilities (74% compared with 59%, respectively) ([AIHW – Australian Institute of Health and Welfare\) analysis of the ACWP](#)).

The PIRLS 2016 found that a higher proportion of Year 4 students from more socioeconomically disadvantaged schools experienced frequent bullying than those attending more affluent schools. About 57% of children from underprivileged schools had experienced bullying in the 12 months before the survey (23% experienced bullying about weekly) compared with half (50%) of children from affluent schools (15% about weekly) (Thomson, Hillman et al. 2017).

The ACWP showed that 11% of Year 4 students and 8% of Year 6 students had used bullying-like behaviours against another child in the same school term the survey was conducted.

Australia has made significant efforts to address cyberbullying and promote online safety. Here are some selected sources where more data on different aspects of social media use among preadolescents in Australia can be found:

[Growing Up in Australia: The Longitudinal Study of Australian Children \(LSAC\)](#) is a major study following the development of 10,000 young people and their families from all parts of Australia. Beginning in 2003, it will follow its cohorts up to their adulthood. It offers interesting data, especially in sections Tweens and Teens (conducted 2018, published 2019) and Adolescents Online (published 2021).

Australian Communications and Media Authority (ACMA): The ACMA is the regulatory body responsible for media and communications in Australia. They have conducted several studies on children's online behaviour, including social media use, which is part of their [research programme](#). Their reports provide data on topics such as the types of social media platforms used by preadolescents, the frequency of use, and the risks associated with social media use. An interesting source is their [Trends in online behaviour and technology usage](#) in ACMA's 2020 annual consumer survey.

The Office of the eSafety Commissioner: As mentioned before, it has conducted [several studies](#) on children's online behaviour, including social media use. Their reports provide data on topics such as the risks associated with social media use, the types of cyberbullying experienced by preadolescents, and the strategies used by parents and educators to manage online risks. Some of the research is related to the Digital lives of Aussie teens (ages 12-17) conducted in 2020; Youth and digital dangers (ages 8 – 17) conducted in 2017; Young people and sexting (in cooperation with the UK and New Zealand) all these were based on data from their 2017 Youth Digital Participation Survey. Mind the Gap – dealing with digital parenting (aged 8-17) was conducted in 2021.

The Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS): The ABS is the national statistical agency of Australia. While they do not have specific reports on preadolescents' social media use, as mentioned above, they provide general data on digital technology's use. Their accounts can provide insights into trends in social media use among different age groups.

Some of the key findings from relevant national research carried out in Australia within the last five years focusing on social media use among (pre)adolescents and safety, risk prevention, or cyberbullying:

[Growing Up Digital Australia](#)

This large-scale research project by the Gonski Institute for Education (UNSW – phase 1 -2015-2019; phase 2 - 2021) aims to understand how children in Australia use digital technology, including social media. The project has published several reports that provide data on preadolescents' social media use, including the types of platforms they use, the amount of time they spend on social media, and their experiences of cyberbullying. It found that preadolescents aged 8-12 in Australia spend an average of 12 hours weekly on social media platforms. The study also found that preadolescents who spent more time on social media were more likely to experience cyberbullying, with girls being more affected than boys. Additionally, the study found that many preadolescents lacked the skills to navigate online risks and that parents and educators needed more support to help children manage online risks.

[Australian Child Wellbeing Project](#)

This study conducted by the Australian Council for Educational Research (Redmond et al., 2016) found that 75% of preadolescents aged 8-14 in Australia reported using social media, with Facebook and YouTube being the most popular platforms. The study also found that preadolescents who spent more time on social media reported lower levels of well-being, including lower levels of satisfaction with their life and lower levels of positive emotions. It worked with a sample of students in Years 4 (age 10), 6 (age 12), and 8 (age 14) and was completed during Term 3, 2014, in 180 schools across Australia.

More than 5,400 students participated in the survey, which collected valuable information on various aspects of young people's wellbeing.

1.3. Good practice examples

In the following text, we list some examples of how schools in Australia are addressing the phenomenon of social media:

Office of the eSafety Commissioner

Children - [The Young and eSafe \(YES\) program](#) is a youth-focused web platform designed to engage and empower young people to take control of their online experiences. It is based on the five key themes of resilience, respect, empathy, responsibility and critical thinking, and provides young people advice and support for dealing with online pressures.

Parents and carers – [eSafety Parents](#) is an online information hub that educates parents and carers on the risks their children face online. It also suggests initiating conversations with children on these risks and other online safety topics.

[Teachers](#) - The Office has developed a range of school-based educational resources and programmes to assist teachers in guiding their students on becoming responsible digital citizens. These are created by the Office's in-house team of former educators and developed in conjunction with certification bodies and teachers.

Community groups - The [eSafety Outreach Program](#) promotes online safety and the building of digital citizenship skills across the broader Australian community. This ranges from training and resource support for the classroom to frontline services for various community groups across Australia, including mental health and youth workers, foster carers, law enforcement and community libraries.

[Digital Citizenship Programmes](#)

Many schools in Australia have implemented digital citizenship programmes (2018 – 2020) that teach students about responsible online behaviour, including social media use (Dezuanni, 2022). These programmes typically cover cyberbullying, privacy, and online etiquette. For example, some schools have implemented the eSmart Schools programme, which provides a framework for schools to promote digital citizenship and online safety.

Social Media Policies

Some schools have developed policies that regulate the use of social media by students and staff. These policies typically outline the expectations for appropriate online behaviour and the consequences for violating the policy. For example, some schools have policies prohibiting using social media during school hours or requiring students to use social media responsibly and respectfully. Here is an example for [New Youth South Wales](#).

Online Safety Education

Many schools in Australia are incorporating online safety education into their curriculum. This education can include online privacy, cybersecurity, and safe social media use. For example, some schools have developed lesson plans that teach students how to identify and respond to cyberbullying. That is happening with the [support of the eSafety Commissioner](#).

Parent Education

Some schools also educate parents on promoting responsible social media use at home. This education can include setting limits on screen time, monitoring online behaviour, and discussing online safety with children. For example, some schools have held parent information sessions on social media and online security. Once again, it is mainly targeted by the [eSafety Commissioner providing many programmes, tips and articles](#). Some of the existing pedagogical and educational approaches to digital and social media literacy in Australia include:

Australian Curriculum

The Australian Curriculum includes a digital technologies curriculum, which aims to develop students' digital literacy skills. This curriculum includes data representation, algorithms, programming, digital citizenship, and online safety. In addition, the general capabilities of the Australian Curriculum include ICT capability, which focuses on developing students' skills in using digital technologies.

Professional Development for Educators

Many schools and education organisations in Australia provide professional development opportunities for educators to improve their digital and social media literacy skills. These opportunities can include workshops, conferences, and online courses. For example, the [Australian Council for Educational Research](#) provides professional learning opportunities for educators to enhance their digital literacy knowledge and online safety.

1.4. Legislation and regulation

Legislation and regulatory frameworks in Australia related to the use, misuse, and abuse of social media:

The Privacy Act 1988

This Act covers organisations with an annual turnover of over \$3 million and some other organisations operating in Australia. If the online social network used is such an organisation, then the Privacy Act protects the shared personal information on it.

The Criminal Code Act 1995

This federal law contains provisions that make it an offence to use a carriage service to menace, harass or cause offence. This includes using social media platforms to send threatening or abusive messages to others.

The Criminal Code Amendment Act of 2019

The Criminal Code Amendment (Sharing of Abhorrent Violent Material) Act 2019 (the Act) came into force on 6 April 2019. The Act creates new offences under the Criminal Code Act 1995 (Cth) to reduce the misuse of online platforms by perpetrators of violence.

The Enhancing Online Safety Act 2015

This federal law established the Office of the eSafety Commissioner, which promotes online safety for all Australians. The law gives the eSafety Commissioner the power to issue removal notices to social media companies for harmful or offensive content and impose civil penalties for non-compliance.

The Australian Privacy Principles (APPs)

These principles are part of the Privacy Act 1988 and provide guidelines for collecting, using, and disclosing personal information by Australian organisations, including social media companies. The APPs require organisations to obtain consent for collecting personal data and to take reasonable steps to protect that information from misuse, interference, and loss.

The Australian Communications and Media Authority (ACMA)

The ACMA is a government agency regulating Australia's communications and media industries. The ACMA has the power to investigate and enforce compliance with regulations related to social media, including advertising standards and content classification.

1.5. Other sources of support

In the following text, we describe some selected internet information portals that support initiatives that address social media, cyberbullying and related issues among pre-adolescents in Australia:

ReachOut.com - an online mental health organisation that provides support and resources for young people in Australia. Their website includes information on cyberbullying, social media, and online safety.

Kids Helpline - a counselling service for young people in Australia. Their website includes information on cyberbullying, online safety, and resources for parents and educators.

[Bullying. No Way!](http://Bullying.NoWay!) - an initiative of the Australian government to prevent and respond to bullying in schools. Their website includes information on cyberbullying, resources for educators, and support for parents and students.

Australian Cyber Security Centre - a government agency that provides resources and support for cybersecurity in Australia. Their website includes information on online safety, cybersecurity, and resources for parents and educators.

[National Centre Against Bullying \(NCAB\)](http://National Centre Against Bullying (NCAB)) - a non-profit organisation that provides resources and support for young people experiencing bullying and cyberbullying. It offers information and support for all the concerned groups – parents, educators and children. It provides various programmes such as eSmart, eSmart Schools, Digital Licence, Children Ahead, and Media Literacy Lab.

1.6. Conclusions

Cyberbullying is a significant problem in Australia, as it is in many other countries worldwide. Cyberbullying can take many forms, including sending threatening or abusive messages, spreading rumours or gossip, sharing embarrassing photos or videos, and posting hurtful comments on social media. The Australian government, schools, and organisations have been taking steps to address the issue of cyberbullying and provide support for victims.

The Australian government has implemented several measures to address cyberbullying, including laws that criminalise cyberbullying and online harassment. The Enhancing Online Safety Act, which came into effect in 2015, established the Office of the eSafety Commissioner responsible for promoting online safety and addressing online bullying, harassment, and abuse. The Act also includes

provisions for removing harmful online content, issuing takedown notices, and imposing fines on individuals or companies that do not comply.

Schools in Australia have also taken steps to address cyberbullying by implementing policies and programs promoting positive online behaviour and supporting victims. Many schools have established online safety programs that educate students about the dangers of cyberbullying and teach them how to respond if they or someone they know is a victim. Some schools have also implemented counselling services to support students affected by cyberbullying.

Australia's significant advantage is its vast government and non-government organisations supporting cyberbullying victims and promoting online safety.

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2. Belgium

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2.1. Statistical data

Belgium has a population of approximately 11.6 million inhabitants (Statbel, 2023). Children under the age of 15 represent around 17% of the total population, making preadolescents, generally defined as children aged 10–14, a significant demographic group within the Belgian school system (Statbel, 2022).

Demographic patterns vary considerably across the country. The proportion of children under 15 is lowest in the Flemish Region (around 16%), higher in the Walloon Region (approximately 17%), and highest in the Brussels-Capital Region, where nearly one in five residents is under the age of 15 (Statbel, 2022). These regional differences are particularly relevant in the Belgian context, as policies related to education, media, and youth are not managed at regional level but by linguistic Communities, which overlap differently with the regional population structure.

Belgium is a highly connected country with near-universal access to digital technologies. According to DataReportal (2023), more than 95% of the population had access to the internet in early 2023, and mobile connectivity was widespread, with the number of mobile subscriptions exceeding the total population. Broadband access, including mobile broadband, was available to the vast majority of households.

Social media use is also highly prevalent. In January 2023, DataReportal estimated that approximately three quarters of the Belgian population were active social media users (DataReportal, 2023). However, as in many European countries, official national statistics do not systematically capture social media use among children below the age of 13, due both to platform age restrictions and data protection regulations.

As a result, quantitative insights into preadolescents' online practices rely largely on European comparative surveys, most notably EU Kids Online. These data indicate that Belgian children aged 11-13 commonly access the internet daily, predominantly via smartphones, and that social media platforms, video-sharing services, and online games play an important role in their everyday social interactions (Smahel et al., 2020). At the same time, a non-negligible proportion of preadolescents report exposure to online risks, including cyberbullying, harmful content, and unwanted contact.

2.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

National research on social media use among preadolescents in Belgium is characterised by a combination of European comparative studies and community-level research, reflecting the country's institutional and linguistic structure.

In line with this, media literacy and youth-related initiatives are in fact primarily organised at the language Community level: in the Flemish Community, a key public actor is Mediawijs (the Flemish Knowledge Centre for Digital and Media Literacy, operating within imec vzw and funded on the initiative of the Flemish Minister for Media); in the Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles, the Conseil supérieur de l'éducation aux médias (Higher Council for Media Education; CSEM) operates as a public

body created by decree; and in the German-speaking Community, media literacy is supported by public services including the Medienzentrum, which is linked to the Ministry of the German-speaking Community.

Therefore, while no single national dataset focuses exclusively on children under 13, several well-established research streams provide consistent insights into young people's online practices and associated risks. The following section presents evidence from EU Kids Online at European level, and from Mediawijs and the CSEM for the Flemish- and French-speaking Communities. By contrast, no comparable publicly available research specifically addressing preadolescents' social media use was identified for the German-speaking Community at the time of writing.

EU Kids Online

Belgium participates in the EU Kids Online network, which remains one of the most comprehensive sources of comparative data on children's online experiences in Europe. The EU Kids Online 2020 survey is based on a large-scale study of children aged 9–16 conducted across 19 European countries (data collected 2017–2019), offering a robust comparative framework for understanding online practices, risks and opportunities (Smahel et al., 2020).

The study highlights that social media, video-sharing platforms, and online games play a central role in children's peer communication and leisure activities. At the same time, EU Kids Online highlights children's exposure to online risks, including harmful content and negative interactions. For example, among older children (12–16) in the Flemish dataset reported within the EU Kids Online 2020 international report, 20% reported seeing hate messages at least monthly, while 16% reported seeing gory/violent images at least monthly (with similarly elevated figures for drug-related content) (Smahel et al., 2020).

Consistent with broader European trends, the data indicate gender- and age-related differences in the types of online experiences and vulnerabilities reported. Girls more frequently report experiences related to social pressure, appearance-based comparison, and relational forms of online aggression, while boys are more often exposed to risks linked to gaming environments and competitive online interactions (Smahel et al., 2020). Overall, EU Kids Online also shows that a sizeable share of children report being bothered or upset by something online, with considerable variation across countries, underlining the importance of addressing online risks already at preadolescent age (Smahel et al., 2020).

Research in the Flemish Community: Mediawijs and Apestaartjaren

In the Flemish Community, one of the most important sources of empirical evidence is the Apestaartjaren research programme, coordinated by Mediawijs in collaboration with academic partners. Apestaartjaren is a recurring large-scale study on children's and young people's media use, with editions published regularly. The most recent data available at the time of this report date from Apestaartjaren 2022 (Mediawijs et al., 2022). In addition, Mediawijs and partners publish complementary monitoring outputs that help interpret children's everyday media use and parental perspectives (Mediawijs, 2023).

The Apestaartjaren findings show that children in late primary school increasingly engage with social media platforms, messaging apps, and video-sharing services, often before the official minimum age. Smartphone ownership is widespread, and digital media are deeply embedded in everyday routines,

including communication with friends, entertainment, and school-related activities. For instance, in a large 2023 survey of parents (Flanders/Brussels), 30% of 9–12-year-olds were reported to use social media with their own account, and a further 18% reportedly used social media via an account managed by a parent. In the same age group, parents reported especially frequent use of WhatsApp (52%), followed by TikTok (39%) and Snapchat (36%) (Mediawijs, 2023).

The research also points to concerns related to online well-being, including exposure to negative interactions, pressure to be constantly available, and difficulties in managing privacy and boundaries. In the same parental survey, 67% of parents of 9–12-year-olds agreed that their child “uses too much social media”, and 65% reported that their child has difficulty stopping (Mediawijs, 2023). While many children are also reported to have positive experiences online, findings from Apestaartjaren and related Mediawijs monitoring show that increased exposure and frequent use do not necessarily correspond to higher levels of digital or critical media literacy, reinforcing the need for structured educational interventions (Mediawijs et al., 2022; Mediawijs, 2023).

Research in the French Community: CSEM and complementary studies

In the French-speaking Community (Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles), research and guidance on children’s media use is often conducted or coordinated through the CSEM, a public body created by decree and tasked with supporting and developing media education initiatives, in collaboration with universities and other recognised resource centres. The CSEM also publishes short syntheses to frame emerging issues and their educational implications (CSEM, 2021).

CSEM outputs emphasise that children and preadolescents are increasingly confronted with complex media environments characterised by algorithmic content, social media dynamics, and blurred boundaries between information, entertainment, and advertising (CSEM, 2021). For example, a 2021 CSEM *Éclairages* publication discusses the growing attention to “kids” versions of social platforms and the educational questions raised by early exposure to social networking logics (CSEM, 2021). Research discussed within CSEM publications, drawing on academic work conducted by universities such as the Université de Liège and the Université catholique de Louvain, reinforces this perspective, highlighting patterns similar to those observed in the Flemish Community, including early social media use, uneven levels of critical understanding, and significant exposure to online risks among younger users (CSEM, 2021).

Together, these studies stress the importance of media education as a citizenship competence, rather than a purely technical skill, in line with the conceptual framework promoted by the CSEM. Particular attention is paid to issues of representation, online harassment, and the emotional impact of social media, especially among younger users who may lack the cognitive and emotional resources to critically interpret online interactions (CSEM, 2021).

2.3. Good practice examples

Belgium does not operate a single national programme addressing social media use and risks among preadolescents. Instead, good practices are largely developed and implemented at Community level, in line with the distribution of competences for education, culture and media literacy. Across the three linguistic Communities, public or publicly mandated institutions play a central role in coordinating initiatives, developing resources, and supporting schools, educators, families and young people.

Flemish Community: Mediawijs

In the Flemish Community, [Mediawijs](#) plays a central role in translating research and monitoring evidence into practice. Building on findings from initiatives such as Apestaartjaren and MediaNest, Mediawijs supports schools, libraries, youth organisations and educators through a wide range of evidence-based educational resources, training opportunities, and large-scale awareness initiatives addressing online safety, digital well-being, disinformation and responsible social media use.

Mediawijs' good practices emphasise critical thinking and reflection on media use, with particular attention to the social and ethical dimensions of digital environments. Rather than focusing on technical skills alone, interventions promote children's and preadolescents' ability to interpret online content, manage interactions, and understand the broader societal implications of media platforms.

A key characteristic of the Mediawijs approach is the systematic integration of research and practice. Monitoring data are explicitly used to inform guidance materials and policy-oriented recommendations, ensuring that educational interventions respond to empirically identified needs and emerging risks among younger users.

Concrete examples of Mediawijs' good practices include the development and dissemination of EDUbox educational toolkits, created in collaboration with public and educational partners (e.g. VRT, imec) and designed for use in primary and lower secondary education. Relevant examples include [EDUbox Sociale media](#), which supports reflection on how social media shape everyday life and social interaction; [EDUbox Nepnieuws](#), which addresses misinformation and disinformation by helping pupils distinguish between facts, opinions and misleading content; and [EDUbox Data en privacy](#), which focuses on personal data, online tracking and digital rights. These materials provide ready-to-use, age-appropriate classroom resources that encourage discussion and critical analysis rather than passive consumption.

In addition, Mediawijs develops and curates teaching materials explicitly targeting critical information skills, opinion formation and fact-checking, such as formats and learning tracks including [Criticat](#), [Opinionmakers](#), [Factcheckers](#), and [Newsmakers](#), addressing the role of influencers and algorithms in shaping online visibility and public debate. Through lesson plans, toolkits and guided activities available via the [mediawijs.be](#) platform, educators are supported in helping preadolescents critically assess online content, recognise sponsored or manipulative communication, and reflect on their own participation in digital environments.

Mediawijs also places strong emphasis on teacher professional development, offering pedagogical guidance, training pathways and practical toolkits, such as [Media Coach](#), [No Cap](#), and [First Aid for Cyberbullying](#). These resources help teachers address concrete classroom challenges related to social media use, online conflicts, cyberbullying and digital well-being, reinforcing the understanding of media literacy as an educational and citizenship competence rather than a purely technical skill, and aligning classroom practice with broader educational and citizenship objectives.

French-speaking Community: CSEM

In the French-speaking Community (Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles), the [CSEM](#) plays a central role in structuring and supporting media education practices. As a public body created by decree, the CSEM acts as a strategic hub for media education, coordinating recognised resource centres, supporting educators, and advising public authorities on media education policies.

Good practices promoted within the CSEM framework conceptualise media education as a citizenship competence, rather than a purely technical skill. Particular emphasis is placed on critical interpretation, representation, participation, and the emotional and social dimensions of media use, in line with the French-speaking Community's long-standing approach to media education.

A key characteristic of the CSEM approach is its role as a knowledge broker between academic research and educational practice. Drawing on research conducted by universities and specialised centres, the CSEM synthesises evidence and translates it into guidance materials, pedagogical tools and policy-oriented recommendations that respond to the needs of children and preadolescents.

Concrete examples of CSEM-supported good practices include the publication of the [Éclairages series](#), which provides concise, accessible analyses of emerging media phenomena relevant to children and young people. Titles such as [Les réseaux sociaux pour les enfants](#) (Social media for children) offer educators and families conceptual frameworks and practical guidance for addressing early social media use, online visibility, and influence dynamics in educational settings.

In addition, the CSEM plays a coordinating role in the recognition and support of Media Education Resource Centres ([Centres de ressources en éducation aux médias](#)), which develop and disseminate pedagogical materials, training activities and classroom tools across the Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles. Through this network, coordinated by the CSEM in collaboration with organisations such as the Centre d'Autoformation et de formation continuée, Capmédia, and Média Animation ASBL, teachers gain access to structured resources and professional support adapted to different educational levels, including late primary and lower secondary education.

The CSEM also supports large-scale awareness and reflection initiatives, such as those linked to the [#Génération2020](#) study, which inform educational practice by highlighting patterns of early digital and social media use among children. By linking empirical evidence to pedagogical guidance, these initiatives contribute to coherent and sustained media education practices within schools and non-formal education contexts.

German-speaking Community: Medienzentrum

In the German-speaking Community, good practices related to media literacy and children's media use are supported primarily through public services rather than large-scale programmes. A central role is played by the [Medienzentrum der Deutschsprachigen Gemeinschaft](#) (Media Centre of the German-speaking Community), based in Eupen and institutionally linked to the Ministry of the German-speaking Community.

The Medienzentrum functions as a public media and resource centre, providing access to a wide range of media materials, audiovisual resources and educational content for schools, educators and families. Through its lending services, curated collections and support activities, the centre contributes to creating favourable conditions for media education within the German-speaking Community.

In addition to access to media resources, the Medienzentrum supports media-pedagogical activities addressed to schools and educational settings, such as class visits, guided activities and workshops. While these initiatives are not always structured as large-scale or standardised programmes, they represent an important institutional support framework for introducing children and preadolescents to media awareness and responsible media use.

Although operating at a smaller scale, reflecting the size of the German-speaking Community in the country, the Medienzentrum represents a stable and institutionalised infrastructure through which media education initiatives can be implemented locally. Its role illustrates how community-level services can effectively support media literacy even in contexts where extensive age-specific research data are not available.

Other initiatives

In addition to the institutions with a formal mandate in media education described above, a number of complementary initiatives and actors contribute to the Belgian ecosystem addressing children's and preadolescents' online experiences.

[Betternet](#) (Safer Internet Centre Belgium) operates as part of the European Better Internet for Kids framework and focuses primarily on awareness-raising, prevention and support related to online risks affecting children and young people. Its activities include educational resources for schools and families, national awareness campaigns such as Safer Internet Day, and support services addressing issues such as cyberbullying and harmful online content. While Betternet's core mandate is centred on online safety and protection rather than media education as such, it represents an important complementary actor within the broader landscape.

In the French-speaking Community, [Média Animation ASBL](#) plays a particularly active role as a recognised media education resource centre and long-standing partner of the CSEM. The organisation develops pedagogical materials, training activities for educators, and applied research on children's and young people's media practices, including initiatives such as #Génération2020. Through its close collaboration with the CSEM, Média Animation contributes directly to the translation of research and policy orientations into educational practice.

Finally, public service media organisations, notably [VRT](#) in the Flemish Community and [RTBF](#) in the French-speaking Community, also contribute to media education efforts through their educational missions. In collaboration with media education actors, public broadcasters support the development of news literacy and critical media understanding among young audiences, including through educational content, classroom-oriented resources and partnerships with schools. These activities complement community-level media education frameworks by linking media production, journalism and education.

2.4. Legislation and regulation

Belgium applies the full range of European Union legislation relevant to children's online protection, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD), and the Digital Services Act (DSA). These frameworks establish obligations concerning data protection, platform accountability, transparency, and the protection of minors from harmful or inappropriate content.

At federal level, Belgian criminal law addresses behaviours such as harassment, hate speech, threats and certain forms of cybercrime, which may also occur in online environments and are addressed under general criminal provisions. In addition, schools are subject to a general legal duty to ensure a safe learning environment, which, according to policy guidance and educational practice, is

increasingly understood to include protection from cyberbullying, online harassment and other digitally mediated risks affecting pupils.

Unlike some other European countries, no single, dedicated law specifically addressing cyberbullying or social media use among minors was identified in the course of this review. Based on the available documentation and sources reviewed, preventive and educational measures related to children's online practices appear to be addressed primarily at Community level rather than regulated uniformly at federal level, reflecting the distribution of competences for education, culture and youth policies.

In the French-speaking Community (Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles), a key legal reference is the Decree of 5 June 2008, which established the CSEM. This decree formally recognises media education as a public policy domain and mandates the CSEM to support schools, coordinate recognised resource centres, and advise public authorities on media education initiatives, including those related to children's and young people's media use.

In the Flemish Community, media literacy and online well-being are addressed through a combination of education and media policies rather than through a single legislative act. Media literacy is embedded in educational objectives, teacher training frameworks and media policy strategies, with Mediawijs recognised as the central public knowledge and coordination centre supporting schools, educators and youth organisations.

In the German-speaking Community, no specific legislation on media education was identified in the course of this review. Instead, support for media literacy and responsible media use appears to be provided through public services and educational policies at community level, notably through the Media Centre of the German-speaking Community (Medienzentrum).

Overall, the Belgian regulatory framework reflects a distributed approach, combining federal criminal law and EU-level platform regulation with community-based educational policies. This results in differentiated but complementary strategies for addressing children's and preadolescents' social media use, with a strong emphasis on education, prevention and institutional support rather than on a single dedicated national law.

2.5. Conclusions

The Belgian context illustrates a highly developed but institutionally differentiated approach to addressing preadolescents' social media use and associated online risks. High levels of digital connectivity and widespread social media use among the general population form the background against which children and preadolescents increasingly engage with digital platforms from an early age. While national statistical data on children under 13 remain limited, European comparative research and community-level studies provide consistent evidence of early and intensive media use, alongside significant exposure to online risks.

Research evidence in Belgium is characterised by a combination of European comparative frameworks and Community-based monitoring, reflecting the country's linguistic and institutional structure. EU Kids Online provides a robust comparative baseline, while initiatives such as Apestaartjaren in the Flemish Community and research and synthesis activities coordinated by the CSEM in the French-speaking Community offer more contextualised insights into children's everyday media practices,

well-being and vulnerabilities, although no dedicated study specifically targeting preadolescents as a distinct age group was identified.

In terms of practice, Belgium does not rely on a single national programme for media education or online safety. Instead, public and publicly mandated institutions at Community level play a central role in translating research evidence into educational practice. Mediawijs in the Flemish Community, the CSEM in the French-speaking Community, and the Mediazentrum of the German-speaking Community illustrate different but complementary institutional models for supporting media literacy, teacher professional development, and school-level interventions. These structures are further complemented by initiatives such as Betternet (Safer Internet Centre Belgium), specialised resource centres, and public service media, which contribute to a broader ecosystem addressing children's online experiences.

From a regulatory perspective, Belgium combines EU-level platform regulation and federal criminal law with Community-based educational policies. Unlike some other European countries, no single dedicated law on cyberbullying or minors' social media use was identified, and preventive and educational measures are primarily addressed through Community competences. This results in a distributed governance model, in which education, prevention and institutional support are prioritised over centralised legislative intervention.

Overall, the Belgian case highlights both strengths and challenges. Strong institutional capacity, well-established research and monitoring frameworks, and a clear emphasis on media education as a citizenship competence provide a solid foundation for addressing preadolescents' social media use. At the same time, the fragmentation of responsibilities and the limited availability of harmonised national data on younger age groups underline the importance of continued coordination, knowledge sharing, and investment in age-appropriate research and educational strategies.

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3. Finland

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3.1. Statistical data

As gathered from the data of Statistics Finland webpage¹, the population of Finland is around 5.5 million people. Of this population, the preadolescent population, which typically refers to children between the ages of 10 and 14, makes up around 5.6% of the total population, which amounts to roughly 314,000 preadolescents (Statistics Finland, 2023). There were 5.39 million Internet users in Finland in January 2022 and Finland's Internet penetration rate stood at 97% of the total population at the start of 2022 (Datareportal, 2023). 84% of young people (between the ages of 16 to 24) use social networking services daily or almost daily and 93% of them have used one or several social networking services in the past 3 months (Statistics Finland, 2023).

According to the report findings from a survey of children aged 9 to 16 from 19 European countries (the data was collected between autumn 2017 and summer 2019 from 25,101 children by national teams from the EU Kids Online network), approximately 79% of the population aged 12 to 14 uses a smartphone several times each day. Key findings from this report state that 97% of Finnish children have access to a smartphone and most of them have their own phone. Although most of the participants are tolerant and see no justifications in violence and bullying, about 40% of them have recently seen bullying or hate speech online (Smahel et al., 2020). More findings regarding the preadolescent children in Finland is shown in the chart below.

Figure 3: Comparison of Finnish children ages 12 to 14 with the average results. Source: EU Kids Online 2020 (Smahel and others, 2020)

¹ Statistics Finland is an independently acting government agency belonging to the administrative sector of the Ministry of Finance.

Regarding the impact of social media on preadolescents in Finland, there is not much research available, but there is research about experiences of social media use among young people in Finland in 2019. Around 93% of young people (aged from 13 to 29) had a social media account and stated that for them social media usage is a way to spend time. The most popular social media platforms among preadolescents in Finland are WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and Snapchat (Statista, 2021).

While most of the experiences with social media are positive, we must remember that there are also risks and challenges associated with their use. These risks include exposure to inappropriate content, cyberbullying and the potential for social comparison and low self-esteem.

3.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

Insurance company mySafety

According to a survey made by insurance company mySafety during the COVID-19 pandemic and posted in the Helsinki Times magazine (Helsinki Times, 2021), cyberbullying has become increasingly common and brutal in Finland. The survey, which had over a thousand respondents, found that almost every second person aged 10 to 17 has faced online harassment. Facebook accounted for 45% of cyberbullying experiences. Other platforms where people faced harassment regularly included WhatsApp (19%), various discussion forums (19%), Snapchat (13%), email (12%), Instagram (11%), online games (11%) and TikTok (8%). Nearly one in 10 reported feeling depressed after being bullied. With nearly every second respondent claiming to be indifferent to online harassment, 41% said they did not take any concrete action against their tormentors.

Nearly half the respondents in the survey were concerned that themselves or their family members would be subjected to offensive behaviour online.

Johanna Abgottspon² suggests that the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic could be at least partially responsible for the increase in cyberbullying as people are spending large amounts of time online.

Nearly 55% of cyberbullying victims said they were attacked because they had shared their opinions, while 29% were bullied because of their appearance. As far as cyberbullying is concerned, the platform where most cyberbullying takes place is Facebook, followed by WhatsApp, various online forums, Snapchat, email, Instagram, online games and TikTok (Helsinki Times, 2021).

Risk factors of cyberbullying and its association with perceived health among Finnish adolescents

This study (Hamal, Neupane & Hannele Rimpela, 2019) focused on the prevalence of cyberbullying dimensions (victims, bullies, seriousness of cyberbullying encountered) and its association with perceived health of Finnish adolescents.

A representative data sample of 12, 14, 16 and 18-year-old Finns from the Adolescent Health and Lifestyle Survey (AHLs) from 2015 was used. Participants responded to the survey via the Internet or a paper questionnaire. Related to health there were three measured areas of cyberbullying consequences (tension, irritation and headaches). Binary logistic regression was used to study the association of age and gender with cyberbullying and the association of perceived health with

² Head of customer operation and marketing at mySafety.

cyberbullying. Multinomial logistic regression was used to study the association of health complaints with cyberbullying. Odds ratio (ORs) and their 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were reported as the measure of association.

Among the respondents 12% were cyber victims, 8.2% cyberbullies and 4.4% encountered serious cyberbullying. Multivariable models adjusted for family structure, father's and mother's education indicated that girls were less likely to become cyberbullies, more likely to encounter serious cyberbullying and become cyber victims compared to boys. Adolescents of age 12–14 years were more likely to become cyberbullies and cyber victims compared to 16–18 years. Girls who perceived their health as poor and reported health complaints were more likely to be involved in cyberbullying or be victims of cyberbullying (Hamal et al., 2019).

Finnish adolescents experience cyberbullying. The likelihood of engaging in cyberbullying was influenced by age and gender, and those who engaged in cyberbullying had a higher likelihood of reporting poor-perceived health and health complaints (Hamal et al., 2019).

The "Protect Children" organisation poll showed that there shall be stronger protection for children and young people in Finland. Based on the Internet and social media usage, there were 1,056 CSAM (child sexual abuse material) reported in 2020 (YLE News, 2022). It is possible to report them via Finnish Hotline Nettivihje (which is Co-funded by the European Union) and to the Finland police (www.poliisi.fi).

3.3. Good practice examples

Digital literacy curriculum

Parental involvement and supervision play a key role in helping preadolescents navigate the risks and challenges of social media use, but also Finland as a state has taken several steps to address the potential negative effects of social media on preadolescents. Firstly, Finland has a comprehensive digital literacy curriculum that is integrated into the national education system. This curriculum is designed to help students learn how to use digital technologies, including social media, in a responsible and safe way. The curriculum covers topics such as online safety, privacy, cyberbullying and critical thinking (Gazdek, 2021). The curriculum offers great possibilities to develop and support students' digital literacies and digital citizenship, however in Finland, teachers have a lot of autonomy to realise the aims of the curriculum, which introduces possibilities as well as responsibilities. Teachers can actualize the curriculum according to their own pedagogical views and their strengths as teachers. Thus, this might result in varying levels of attention to digital literacies (International Literacy Association, 2015).

Yle Oppiminen

Finland has also launched several initiatives aimed at promoting positive online behaviour and reducing the risks associated with social media use. For example, in 2020, the Finnish National Broadcasting Company launched a program called "Yle Oppiminen", which provides digital learning resources for students and teachers. The program includes content on digital literacy and online safety, as well as other content that is adjusted to the interest and lifestyle of the younger population (YLE, 2023).

Online resources for parents

Finland recognizes the importance of parental involvement in promoting safe and responsible social media use. The Finnish government has created online resources for parents, such as the "Parent's Guide to Social Media," which provides tips and advice for supporting children's digital well-being (Better Internet for Kids, 2023). The [Mannerheim League for Child Welfare](#) is a similar Internet page, where parents, children and educators can get a lot of useful data, tips and tricks about children welfare and Internet safety.

KiVaKoulu® cyberbullying program (KiVa)

KiVaKoulu® is an anti-bullying program originating from the University of Turku, which examines bullying as a group process and has its focus on participants' characters. The program's goal is to prevent bullying, victimisation and to successfully mediate cases that have already arisen (Gazdek, 2021).

An interesting fact about anti-bullying programs in Finland is the fact that in 2006 (only two years after Facebook was launched) Finnish Ministry of Education mandated a group to develop an anti-bullying program (Salmivalli et al., 2011). The result of the group was the KiVa program.

The Finnish program against cyberbullying KiVa has been developed by the University of Turku, and is funded by the Ministry of Education and Culture. Program includes children, their parents and their teachers, which shows how important this issue is in Finnish society.

There are three cornerstones of the program: prevention, intervention and monitoring. Prevention focuses on student curriculum, which includes lessons (role-plays, video materials) and online games with concrete examples of unwanted actions. The main purpose of prevention is to keep bullying from happening. Intervention stresses the importance of tools to tackle bullying. Annual monitoring is providing annual surveys for students and school staff in order to provide schools with feedback on improving their anti-bullying activities (Kivaprogram.net, 2023). Research on effectiveness of this program showed significantly lower frequency of cybervictimization with students, who were included in the program (Williford et al., 2012). On the other hand, the control group is almost two times more likely to develop bullying behaviours (Salmivalli et al., 2011; Salmivalli et al., 2013).

The student lessons form the basis of the universal actions in KiVa. The lessons form a continuum lasting for the whole comprehensive education, with key issues taken up repeatedly in Grades 1, 4 and 7 in age-appropriate ways. The lessons also cover topics related to group interaction and respectful communication more widely. A special emphasis, however, is on how the students witnessing bullying can use their potential to reduce it. Indicated actions, on the other hand, refer to tackling the acute cases of bullying by the schools' KiVa teams, consisting of three adults working in the school.

KiVa-program has been evaluated first with a randomised controlled trial (2007-2009) and then during nationwide diffusion across schools (since 2009). KiVa-program has proven to be effective in reducing bullying and victimisation and consequently, in internalising problems. It also led to increases in well-being and school liking among a much wider group of children than just previous victims and bullies. The indicated actions, i.e. discussions between schools' KiVa team members and children involved in bullying has proven to be highly effective. The uptake of the program by Finnish schools has been remarkable, as 90% of all Finnish schools have implemented KiVa between 2009-2013. According to research, at least 1,900 schools are using KiVa actively. In order to prevent a decrease in

implementation over time, some new actions have been adopted to support schools in their efforts. Such actions include newsletters sent to schools, online training about the KiVa program and its implementation, biannual KiVa conference days, quality recommendations provided to schools, regular monitoring of implementation. Besides, the KiVa School of the Year is awarded every year (Eucpn.org, 2023).

3.4. Legislation and regulation

From 1st of July 2010 onwards all the Finnish citizens (the first nation in the world) has a legal right to access a 1Mbps broadband connection (Zeldin, 2010). It is therefore important to offer a proper media education for all the inhabitants, especially children. This is the responsibility of the Ministry of Education and Culture with the Department for Educational Policy and the Department for Cultural, Sport and Youth Policy. Media education is also a part of the library policy (Ministry of Education and Culture Finland, 2013).

As a member of the European Union, Finland must ensure that the requirements for data protection under Finnish law are at least as strict as those set out by EU legislation (Dittmar & Indrenius, 2019).

Under the EU Regulation users of Internet access services have the right to access and distribute information and content and to use and provide applications and services of their choice. Users have this right irrespective of the origin or destination of the information. This principle is also called net neutrality. The Act on Electronic Communication Services 917/2014 (Laki sähköisen viestinnän palveluista) regulates online privacy matters such as the use of cookies and location data (DLA Piper, 2023).

The right to privacy is a fundamental right under the Constitution of Finland (731/1999); thus, it enjoys wide protection. The Finnish data protection authority, Data Protection Ombudsman, is responsible for enforcing data protection legislation in Finland. The Data Protection Ombudsman guides and controls the processing of personal data in Finland and makes decisions on the lawfulness of processing activities. The Data Protection Ombudsman also provides guidance, both to those whose data is being processed and to those processing it. The Data Protection Ombudsman has the right to access and inspect data files to issue directions or make decisions (Dittmar & Indrenius, 2019).

In 2003 the Finnish government resolution on the National Information Security strategy was adopted. Its aim is to enhance the level of trust shown by the general public and by businesses in the services of information society. For this reason, since 2004 every February a Safer Internet Day has been organised by the Finnish Communications Regulatory Authority. The project also fulfils the objectives set by the Ministry of Transport and Communications, outlined in the communications policy strategy, which is to answer new challenges that have arisen through technological development and changes in the operating environment (Hell, 2007).

The Finnish government also amended its legislation and gave the educational system in Finland the right and obligation to make school environments safe from any kind of violence (Gazdek, 2021, p. 21).

Furthermore, Finland defined bullying and legal consequences for the perpetrators. The great support of legislation was considered a huge milestone in fighting cyberbullying in elementary schools in Finland (Gazdek, 2021, p. 22). One of the most common ways the schools are trying to oppose

cyberbullying is investing more in the prevention of it rather than in coping intervention. The most common way of putting an emphasis on prevention is via making restrictions regarding the use of technology (private cell phones) during the classes and denying students of visiting social media during school hours. These policies have been proven to be effective because they are both limiting the students' time spent on social media and reducing opportunities for cyberbullying during school hours but as stated, they are protecting students only when they are in school (Gazdek, 2021, p. 23).

In 2015, the Finnish government incorporated special regulation on social media into its Alcohol Act. The amendment aims to limit the use of social media for alcohol marketing and prevent adolescent drinking by protecting minors from alcohol advertising. The Finnish Alcohol Act restricts the use of social media alcohol advertising in three ways:

1. it forbids the use of interactive games, competitions, and lotteries,
2. it bans the use of user generated content, meaning any material produced by consumers may not be distributed through the alcohol advertiser's social media page,
3. it prohibits content that is intended to be shared by consumers, implying alcohol brands should not encourage consumers to share content that is produced for the purpose of advertising alcohol (Kaupilla, 2019).

There is no specific legislation on cybercrime or cybersecurity, however, several provisions that cover cybercrime can be found in the Criminal Code of Finland (Dittmar & Indrenius, 2019).

3.5. Conclusions

The Finnish approach to addressing the potential negative effects of social media on preadolescents emphasises education, legislation, and parental involvement. The available data suggests that social media use is widespread among preadolescents in Finland and that it is associated with both benefits and risks. While social media can offer opportunities for social connection and entertainment, it can also expose preadolescents to online harassment, inappropriate content and negative health outcomes.

Almost every second person aged 10 to 17 has already faced online harassment with Facebook accounting for 45% of cyberbullying experiences. Among other factors, gender, age and perceived health have been associated with the risks of online harassment and cyberbullying.

Finland demonstrates a wide array of good-practice initiatives devoted to prevention and coping with the acts of cyberbullying. For instance, digital literacy has been addressed directly by the schools in a curricular way, several online resources are available both for students and their parents etc. There is a transnational cyberbullying prevention program (the KiVa program) worth pointing out. The KiVa program has been adopted by most schools in Finland and the program has proven highly effective in preventing the cybervictimization and other forms of cyberbullying threats.

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4. Rhode Island (USA)

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4.1. Statistical data

Rhode Island is geographically the smallest U.S. State. According to the U.S. Bureau of the Census, Rhode Island had a population of 1,097,379 people in 2020, an increase of 4.3% compared to 2010 (State of Rhode Island, Division of Statewide Planning, n.d.). It has 484,474 housing units; the number has increased by 4.3% compared to 2010. Among six age groups (0 to 4, 5 to 19, 20 to 34, 35 to 49, 50 to 64, and 65 and older) the 65+ group was the fastest growing between 2010 and 2020, with its population increasing by 27.2%. The 35 to 49 age group had the 8.9% drop between 2010 and 2020 (USA FACT, n.d.). According to the same source, the number of children aged 5 - 19 decreased in 2020 compared to 2010, from 19.3% to 17.5%. As of 2021, there are 80,153 children aged 5 - 11 and 36,853 aged 12 - 14 in Rhode Island (Kids Count Data Center, n.d.). It has five different counties: Bristol County, Kent County, Newport County, Providence County, and Washington County. It has 24 school districts.

4.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

At the USA level, we can see significant differences in preadolescents' and adolescents' media usage habits. Preadolescents (8-12) are watching television more (65%) and reading for enjoyment (37%) more than adolescents (21%). A more significant number of preadolescents are also playing video games on a smartphone or tablet (47%) than adolescents (38%). Hence, the most significant difference, as expected, can be found in the category of social media usage, while only 17% of preadolescents are using social media compared to 59% of those aged 13-18 (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Share of children and teens in the United States who engaged in selected media and internet activities daily during the coronavirus pandemic as of June 2021, by age group. (Source: Statista, 2021)

Most of Rhode Island's elementary and secondary students do not receive media literacy education, according to findings from a survey and interviews with over 500 educators, parents, and community leaders (Media Education Lab, 2021, p. 1). Researchers Renee Hobbs, Pam Steager, Mary Moen, Rongwei Tang, Tessa Mediano & Jenny Sullivan have conducted 30 interviews with people who provided additional insight on the practice of media literacy education in local school districts. According to the research gathered around Media Education Lab, only 1 in 5 Rhode Island elementary students learn how advertising affects people's attitudes and behaviours. In this research, participants in elementary school were asked to estimate "how many of the young learners in their schools or community have encountered any of these instructional practices during the academic year". Only 17% have answered "most" or "nearly all" that they can interpret different types of advertising to examine how images can be manipulated and then reflect on how advertising affects attitudes and behaviours (p. 8). Furthermore, only 21% of respondents have answered "most" or "nearly all" that they can identify the many different choices that creators make and consider how the design of media messages may influence people's thoughts, feelings, and beliefs. Slightly better knowledge was expressed regarding telling a story or comparing and contrasting between two different forms of media to identify similarities and differences in content, format, target audience and point of view. (p. 8). One of the essential findings of this study is that a certain number of pupils is participating in activities provided by the community, elective courses, and student clubs. However, "media literacy" was available to only 20% of respondents while computer programming was available to 70% of respondents. (p. 14). The research has also revealed that "there are significant disparities between school districts, with some communities offering media literacy education to most students in elementary, middle school and high school, while other communities give students fewer opportunities" (p. 1).

In times of pandemic, the digital literacy competences and skills have been emphasized just like in most other countries. Nevertheless, education in that challenging times has also revealed significant differences between the pupils and teachers. Even at the level of approach and fundamental ICT preconditions, there were differences between counties and districts. Furthermore, the pandemic has spotlighted new challenges for school staff as they were forced to navigate through platforms and adapt to new educational circumstances.

Generally, the implementation of media literacy education programs in local communities is largely contingent upon the interests, experience, knowledge, and talents of educators and school leaders. (Hobbs et al., 2022, p. 191).

In Rhode Island, there was a state-wide campaign to provide professional development in media literacy education to school and public librarians in a collaboration between the University of Rhode Island and the State Office of Library and Information Service (OLIS) with support from the U.S. Institute of Museum and Library Studies (IMLS). The program included the provision of digital badges as school librarians attended workshops and learned about animation, film literacy, and other topics (Moen, 2020, according to Hobbs et al., 2022, pp. 190-191).

Research on cyberbullying is scarce, with a limited scope. Data is provided primarily through the Rhode Island Department of Education and Rhode Island Department of Health through Rhode Island Youth Risk Behaviour Study (2009-2015). In a 2013-2014 report, 10% of Rhode Island Middle School students reported having embarrassing pictures or rumours spread by others electronically, and 12% reported being harassed or bullied on social media (Rhode Island Kids Count, 2016).

“According to overall findings of Dorothy Skierkowski-Foster (2021), 29% of Rhode Island middle and high school students confirmed being bullied at school in the previous year, and 11.7% said they had experienced cyberbullying in the previous three months.” (LLCBuddy, 2023). The Rhode Island Student Survey (RISS) was administered to 22,294 middle and high school students from 25 school districts and 55 schools in Rhode Island from February to April 2018, of which 19,327 students completed the survey. (Skierkowski-Foster, 2021, p. 50). Skierkowski-Foster has presented the results that the percentage of 9th to 12th graders in this sample of Rhode Island schools who acknowledged being a victim of cyberbullying was slightly lower than the national average (11.7% versus 14.9%) (p. 62).

However, compared to EU practice and research approaches such as EU Kids Online network we can't find comprehensive longitudinal research on cyberbullying practices focused predominantly on pre-adolescents. Even this limited research overview had an impact on the legislative approach regarding policy on cyberbullying at the level of school that is further elaborated in the legislation chapter.

4.3. Good practice examples

Media Education Lab

Media Education Lab is a network of co-learners and collaborators. Distinguished scholar Renee Hobbs, University of Rhode Island founded it. It provides support and empowerment to many teachers, students, librarians, and parents in the USA and abroad. Compared to a similar network, it also has a substantial international impact with diverse researchers covering many scientific areas.

They also address policy issues that affect the quality of teaching and learning about media, technology, and popular culture. According to their web site the Media Education Lab has two primary goals:

- (1) Providing public programs, educational services, community outreach and multimedia curriculum resources targeted to the needs of educators and learners in school and after-school settings.
- (2) Developing and implementing a multidisciplinary research agenda to explore the educational impact of media and technology, with a focus on digital and media literacy education as an expanded conceptualization of literacy.

In the last few years, it has become one of the most used nationwide resource databases with teaching resources in many fields of media literacy. They provide instructions and support in different topics related to media literacy: *Youth and Community Media Production, Teaching Media Literacy, News Literacy, Media, Youth and Civic Engagement, Media Literacy in Urban Schools, Media Literacy Advocacy, Games for Online Learning, Digital Literacy, Copyright and Fair Use, Contemporary Propaganda, Girls and Media Culture, International Media Literacy, Media and Health, Media and Family, Measuring Media Literacy, Advertising Literacy*. There are also special programs such as Medialogue on Propaganda – An Online Learning Community for Educators with 309 participants from Germany and USA but also at the international level.

The major event with the most significant participants is their SUMMER INSTITUTE program for “K-12 educators, librarians, college and university faculty leaders of community organizations and media professionals”. This one-week professional development program has been recognized by U.S. National Education Plan. It was established in 2013 and has gathered more than 800 participants since.

Participants receive a 12-credit Graduate Certificate in Digital Literacy. In time of pandemic, they have organized a considerable number of webinars even weekly.

They have provided programs and introduced Digital Literacy to Rhode Island Principals but have also provided new educational programs such as MAKE-A-MINUTE-MOVIE Challenge in 2014.

One of the most interesting teaching materials produced by Media Education Lab is the curriculum for diverse topics. In the last few years, they have focused on activities for propaganda deconstruction. Mind Over Media – Analysing Contemporary Propaganda is a multimedia program and educational channel for effective propaganda deconstruction. European Commission has also supported it. "The Mind Over Media platform enables users to share examples of contemporary propaganda for educational purposes using crowdsourcing. Anyone can upload an example of propaganda and comment on it, considering its potential impact on public opinion. The translations and adaptations of this platform have been co-financed by European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology as part of the Pilot Project – Media Literacy For All Grant agreement no LC-00644630". This platform also offers lesson plans and the complete Mind Over Media Curriculum to teachers at the global level and on Romanian, Belgian, Finnish and Croatian languages. The director of the Media Education Lab is Yonty Friesem, PhD.

The Providence Children's Film Festival

This festival offers parents, families, and the community opportunities to access delightful, challenging films and the skills to be their own creative media makers. They sponsor film screenings, hands-on workshops, summer media literacy programs, community jury events, and the "Be a Cinema Detective" media literacy program (Media Education Lab, 2021 p. 15).

4.4. Other programs and activities

In the Providence Public Schools from 2000-2003, there was established a media literacy program **Media SmART! Providence**. It was federally funded by three institutions – the Department of Education, the National Endowment for the Arts, and the Department of Justice – so it was focused on media literacy and media production as violence prevention tools. In after-school group programs, 8-11-year-olds learned about the use of violence in the media and created their own anti-bullying Public Service Announcements – PSAs and book commercials. The summer teacher training component continued for another two years with leftover funds. Teachers, parents, and students who participated in media literacy activities have gained new skills and practices.

Another unique workshop was on **Deconstructing Disney** by Renee Hobbs and Pamela Steager as part of the Providence Children's Film Festival. That workshop eventually became a resource on the Media Education Lab website. Moreover, as a PCFF partner, they worked with the festival staff to add media literacy components to their website.

NGO scene on media literacy is huge. Most of the activities are covered by **Media Literacy Now RI** – a branch part of the nationwide program focusing on advocacy activities on ML. Pamela Steager is the state coordinator. Her committed work in promoting media literacy has also been recognized by NAMLE (National Association for Media Literacy Education) as she was awarded in 2022. This organization is still advocating to pass legislation about adding ML to the state education program (Media Literacy Now, 2018).

There are also many small-scale activities such as an event for a local **Girls & Boys Club** after-school group as part of a course in Film Education by Renee Hobbs and Pamela Steager. It was focused on a locally produced short film depicting children in their neighborhood and a longer film that was used to model asking the media literacy questions using the tool Media Education Lab Smartphone.

As part of the activities with other stakeholders we need to mention and emphasize a strong connection with librarians, primarily through media production workshops with that age group in local libraries throughout Rhode Island in partnership with the Providence Children's Film Festival and funded through the Rhode Island State Council on the Arts. It was focused on practical skills on producing media content, and participants gained new knowledge and perspectives on media literacy in general.

Librarians' activities

Public and school libraries play a significant role in the promotion of digital media literacy. Providence Public Library is supporting the Digital Literacy Corps. Cranston Public Library's in 2015 opened "The C Lab" a multi-use digital media learning space. This library has also received the "Library of the Year" award by University of Rhode Island. According to the Media Education Lab (2021) The Rhode Island Office of Library and Information Services and the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS) have supported state-wide training programs in media literacy for school and public librarians (Media Education Lab, 2021, p. 15). There are many opportunities for a strategic approach in this field. In times of COVID-19, librarians have provided support to disinformation programs and in general, of the credibility of information.

Legislation and regulation

With or without state laws, implementing ML education into schools requires support from multiple stakeholders. Classroom teachers in all grade levels and content areas have been shown to integrate ML learning activities such as analysing and creating media as cross-curricular skills (Manfra, Holmes, 2020; Stein, Prewett, 2009; Weninger, Hu, Choo, 2017, according to Hobbs et al., 2022, p. 2)

In 2017, Rhode Island's General Assembly passed a law that amends Rhode Island's General Laws by instructing the department of elementary and secondary education to consider, in consultation with national or state-wide organizations, the incorporation of media literacy education into the board of education's basic education program regulations. The Rhode Island Department of Education has yet to make progress in meeting this obligation (Media Education Lab, 2021, p. 2). This was the unique opportunity to include media literacy into curricula at the state level. However, this did not happen. In 4 years, from 2017-2021, most of the activities provided by NGO promoted media literacy along with other advocacy activities.

On 07/08/2021 Governor signed The Civic Literacy Act RI H5028, which requires "that middle and high school students that attend public schools demonstrate proficiency in civics education and would require public schools to provide not less than one student-led civics project in either middle or high school consistent with history and social studies frameworks promulgated by the Rhode Island board of education". Due to many advocacy campaigns before this Act, it was expected that media literacy and/or media education would become a part of this Act but these expectations were not met. Organizations such as Media Education Lab have provided evidence for the implementation of media literacy, but the State of Rhode Island needed to recognize these arguments while introducing The

Civic Literacy Act (Media Education Lab, 2021). According to the research provided by CIRCLE – Centre for information & research on civic learning and engagement one year after the Act was in place, 53% of the students surveyed said that “civics and/or United States government schoolwork helps them understand what is happening in the world around them”. The media literacy activities or programs were not included as a part of this curriculum.

According to the Stopbullying.gov a federal government website managed by the US Department of Health and Human Services the State of Rhode Island has successfully implemented measures to regulate bullying and cyberbullying in 6 documents – laws and regulations:

- Rhode Island General Laws §16-21-24. Requirements of school safety plans, school emergency response plans, and school crisis response plans.
- Rhode Island General Laws §16-21-33. Safe schools act.
- Rhode Island General Laws §16-21-34. State-wide bullying policy implemented.
- 200 Code of Rhode Island Rules 020-10-1. Basic Education Program.
- 200 Code of Rhode Island Rules 030-10-2. Safe School Act – State-wide Bullying Policy.
- 216 Code of Rhode Island Rules 020-10-4. School Health Programs.

4.5. Conclusions

Although media literacy education is still not included in the formal school curriculum at the state level, there are many activities focused on children, parents, librarians, and school associates but also for the general audience. Even from 2008, we could see state interventions for cyberbullying prevention and policies showcased by 6 different laws/regulations. It happened due to many cyberbullying examples as in many other states. The so-called protectionist approach, however, cannot provide critical reflection in all other important media literacy areas. But Rhode Island also has a media literacy education excellence centre – Media Education Lab. Its resources are used far beyond Rhode Island and this networking platform has initiated many new programs and activities worldwide. It is still providing support for many teachers at the national and international levels. ASAP could profit from the different types of curricula prepared and implemented by experts from different backgrounds. All these materials are available publicly, and some of the materials are even translated to the partner languages of our project.

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5. Spain

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5.1. Statistical data

A general overview: Spain's digitalization in numbers

Similarly to other European countries, Spain's media landscape underwent a deep change since the beginning of the millennium due to digitalization and the rise of digital media. These shifts changed media consumption patterns with traditional media losing to digital media, particularly among younger generations.

According to 2022 data from the National Statistics Institute, the population of Spain in July 2022 was 47,615,034 inhabitants. Children aged between 10 and 14 years old were 2,517,373. The CEU Demographic Observatory's October 2021 report presents an ageing population – in January 2021, 6.1% of the population was 80 years old or older (CEU, 2021).

In 2023, Spain had about 40.7 million users of social networks – 85.6% of its population (Una vida online, n.d.). The social network with the most users was YouTube – 40.7 million users – and each person used on average 6 different social media platforms (Una vida online, n.d.). Around 2.3% of social networks users in Spain are aged between 13 and 17 years old – 47.8% are female and 52.2% are male (Una vida online, n.d.).

Data from the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2022, shows that Spain ranks 7th of the 27 EU Member States, with major increases on the integration of digital technology, digital public services and human capital comparatively to the last report. The country is also one of EU's leaders in terms of connectivity, ranking 3rd (DESI, 2022). In terms of basic digital skills, the rate of people in Spain having at least basic digital skills is above the EU average (64% compared to 54%), a number that has been increasing over the past years (DESI, 2022). Though, the number of employed ICT experts is slightly below EU average (4.1% compared to 4.5%) – this aspect has impacts in terms of growth and productivity in small and medium-sized enterprises.

Young people, Internet and digital devices

Similarly to other countries, there is no extensive research focused on preadolescents. Therefore, the following studies present trends and data related to younger age groups, namely adolescents. Recent studies show that also for young Spaniards, internet and ICTs assume a fundamental role in their socialisation processes - the different ways through which individuals learn and assimilate the values, beliefs, norms, behaviours, and social skills that are prevalent in their culture or society (Parke et al., 2008). In 2019, Fundación FAD Juventude (FAC) published the study "ICT and its Influence on Adolescent Socialisation". The study analysed the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) by Spanish teenagers and its impact on their socialisation. The study shows that the use of smartphone is generalised among young people (89.8%), as is the laptop (75.7%) and the tablet (68.8%) – with kids owning their personal devices (Ballesteros & Picazo, 2019). The study presents a comparison between young people and the general population, showing that boys and girls report

being more equipped in terms of devices than the general population (aged 15 and over), especially in terms of the tablet (68.8% of young people own it compared to 41.7% of the general population) (Ballesteros & Picazo, 2019). The report shows that the activities conducted on the internet more frequently are related to leisure – listening and downloading music (75.6%), visiting webpages for fun (48.3%) and also keep in touch with people (45.8%) (Ballesteros & Picazo, 2019). Similar data is exposed by a study by Megías and Rodríguez (2018). The authors also point out that young people tend to have a positive view of their digital competencies, with around 92% considering they are more competent than their parents and 81% thinking they are more competent than their teachers.

Data from the EU Kids Online report 2020 also points out that Spanish children's engagement with online communication and entertainment activities increased since 2015. Their preferred activities are communicating with family and friends (70%), and leisure activities (e.g. listening to music (63%), watching video clips (55%) and playing online (46%)). They frequently get bored online (33% of the children inquired in the questionnaire) (Smahel et al., 2020).

IAB's annual Social Media Study 2022 reports that around 93% of the Spanish population aged between 12 and 70 are internet users and that 85% used social media (IAB, 2022). As to youth, the Youth in Spain 2020 Report shows that the degree of connectivity of young people is enormously high, as well as their recourse to different online practices ranging from playing video games and using social networks to doing schoolwork (Diáz et al., 2021). In addition, the same report shows that social networks play a very important role in the leisure of Spanish youth – connecting to social networks to share content or being part of virtual communities in a broad sense is one of the most marked practices of young people, especially after the generalisation of smartphones (Diáz et al., 2021). In general terms, the Youth 2020 Report finds that young people between 14 and 19 years of age use the Internet for two activities in tandem: connecting to social networks such as Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, Tik-tok (96.3%), listening to music and watching series and films online (94.7%) and doing work on the Internet (86%) (Diáz et al., 2021).

5.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

Dangers, Risks and Harmful consequences of the use of Digital Media

The study "Yo a eso no juego - Bullying y cyberbullying en la infancia" conducted in 2016 by the NGO Save the Children on bullying and cyberbullying among 12 to 16 years old kids attending public schools (a total of 21,500 students) points out that 1 in each 10 students refers to have been a victim of bullying and that 7% of the students refers to have been abused through the internet or the mobile phone (Sastre et al., 2016). The report also shows that kids frequently change positions between abused and abusers – 5.4% of the respondents recognized to have abused someone and 3.3% refers to having conducted online abuse (Sastre et al., 2016). The more frequently victimised groups are girls and younger children (Sastre et al., 2016).

The study "ICT and its Influence on Adolescent Socialisation" also examined the relationship between ICT use and well-being among teenagers (Ballesteros & Picazo, 2019). Results from the interviews conducted within the study suggest that excessive use of ICT can be a risk factor for mental health problems, namely anxiety and depression (Ballesteros & Picazo, 2019).

In terms of parental involvement in their teenagers' ICT use, the study found that parents play an important role in mediating their children's use of technology. Parents who set clear rules and limits

around technology use were more likely to have teenagers who use technology responsibly and experience fewer negative outcomes (Ballesteros & Picazo, 2019).

Data from the EU Kids Online report 2020 warns that comparatively to boys, girls access more to aggressive or violent content online, namely content related to ways of physically hurting themselves (6% vs 2%), committing suicide (5% vs 1%), ways of being very thin (4% vs 1%) and hate messages (12% vs 4%) (Smahel et al., 2020). The report stresses that, due to this, teen girls have found themselves in online situations that bothered them (40%) more often than boys (29%) (Smahel et al., 2020). Eu Kids Online Spain also underlines that Spanish parents tend to have a more positive attitude and encourage boys to explore online; whereas they tend to be more restrictive when it comes to girls and their online life (Smahel et al., 2020).

5.3. Good practice examples

[PDA Bullying Platform](#)

The PDA BULLYING Platform is a network of institutions, established in 2016, that promote good practices for prevention, detection and action against abuse, cyberbullying and other forms of abuse that occur in childhood and adolescence. In addition to promoting the establishment of a network for sharing information and knowledge, the platform promotes certification of centres, projects, educational resources, and other institutions or initiatives through an audit and advisory process that aims to identify needs and implement improvements to combat the spread of cyberbullying and other forms of violence in these contexts. It also provides a set of tools and resources in free access on these issues.

You can visit the platform [here](#).

[Aprender a Mirar Foundation](#)

The Aprender a Mirar Foundation is a non-profit organisation under the protection of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport, which works for the defence of audio-visual media users, especially children and young people.

The foundation provides resources and informative texts on these themes. Through its platform it is also possible to make requests for support or share reports of cases of online abuse.

In Aprender a Mirar's [platform](#) you can know more about its activities, resources and training.

[CIBERBULLYING - Resource guide for schools in cases of cyberbullying](#)

Guide prepared by the Defensor del Menor in the Community of Madrid, an entity belonging to the High Commission of the Assembly of Madrid. Its mission is to safeguard and promote the rights of minors in the Community of Madrid, in accordance with the powers entrusted to it by this Law.

This guide provides information on the phenomenon of cyberbullying, the legal classification of certain online behaviours, how to act in specific situations, the need for prevention and intervention protocols. It also offers didactic units to be developed in the classroom to work with students on this problem and activities to be carried out with parents. Finally, it offers normative references to help reflect on an issue that is becoming increasingly visible and worrying.

This publication can be of use for teachers, parents and students, and can help to ensure that tools as interesting as new technologies do not end up becoming weapons to be used, in this case, against classmates or acquaintances. The guide is available in free access [here](#).

[Good practice manual for the prevention of cyberbullying and other online risks and violence](#)

Guide resulting from the intervention project on cyberbullying and online risks and violence Te pongo un reto: #RedesConCorazón. The project was implemented during 2019, having covered around 1,500 students, 74 educators and 31 families, spread across 4 secondary schools and 3 socio educational institutions from the Madrid region. The guide is aimed at various educational audiences and aims to explain the different forms of violence and aggression that occur in online spaces. It also presents good practices that can be applied or reproduced in other contexts.

[Instituto Nacional de Ciberseguridad \(National Cybersecurity Center\)](#)

The Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute (INCIBE) works to build digital trust, enhance cybersecurity and resilience, and to contribute to the digital marketplace in a way that promotes the safe use of the Spanish cyberspace. Among its many activities INCIBE promotes training, awareness campaigns, and the Cibercooperantes program – an initiative that promotes the active collaboration of individual people interested in the dissemination of cybersecurity, through training with centres, associations, organisations or individuals that require this type of action. The goal of this initiative is to engage society to fight cyberbullying and raise awareness towards the impacts of violent and aggressive online behaviours. INCIBE also makes available various channels that work as hotlines/helpines that citizens can use to report situations of abuse and ask for help.

5.4. Legislation and regulation

DESI 2022 points out that Spain's Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRP) is one of the most ambitious regarding digital challenges and innovation - 28.2% of the budget is allocated to digital (EUR 19.6 billion). Areas particularly in focus in Spain's RRP are businesses digitalization and strengthening the digital skills of people, improving digital connectivity across the country's territory, continuing the digitalisation of the public services, and supporting digital-related Research & Development (R&D) and the deployment of digital technologies.

Spain adopted a set of guidelines to contribute to the country's digital objectives: the Digital Spain 2025 strategy; the National Digital Competences Plan; the strategy for the promotion of 5G technology; the SME Digitalisation Plan 2021-2025; and the national AI strategy. DESI also notes that by 2022, relevant policy developments will include the new Law on Telecommunications that will transpose into national law the EU Directive establishing the European Electronic Communications Code, as well as the Law on 5G cybersecurity.

According to a country map profile developed by Better Internet for Kids (Better Internet for Kids, 2021), various regulations and legislation have been developed to protect and empower Spanish citizens against the dangers perpetuated by online environments. These include:

- The Law on the Comprehensive Protection of Children and Adolescents against Violence (approved on May 20th 2021) – this legislation incorporates all previous provisions to combat violence against children and adolescents and consolidates their rights and the State's commitment towards protecting them. It includes measures aimed at preventing, detecting

and repairing the damage caused by violence against children and adolescents, while increasing societal awareness of this issue.

- Law 26/2015, of 28 July – legislation that modifies the children and adolescent protection system of 07/2015 and aims to strengthen the protection of children and young people in the country. One of the main objectives of the law is to improve the response of the Spanish authorities to cases of child abuse, neglect, and exploitation. The law recognizes the importance of respecting the views and opinions of children and young people in decisions that affect their lives.
- Organic Law 3/2018, of 5 December, on the Protection of Personal Data and guarantee of digital rights – among other aspects, it establishes the right to education (Art. 83) and the protection of children on the Internet (Art. 92).
- The National Cybersecurity Strategy 2019 – document that aims to provide a framework for enhancing Spain's cybersecurity capabilities and resilience.
- Organic Law 13/2015, of 5 October, amending the Criminal Procedure Law to strengthen procedural guarantees and regulation technological investigation measures.

Furthermore, the country has an extensive framework to safeguard children's safety as well as to combat the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography. This includes the Law 26/2015 of 28 July on the Protection of Children and Adolescents against Violence and other international treaties (e.g. United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child and the Council of Europe Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse).

5.5. Conclusions

The data collected for the preparation of this report show a path marked by great **concern with awareness of the dangers and impacts of cyberbullying and online violence**. In a country that follows the European digitalisation trend and where the use of social networks is widespread among young people, we can see significant steps to combat cyberbullying and create a safer digital environment for citizens of all ages. **Recognizing the harmful effects of online harassment and the need to protect individuals, particularly young people, the Spanish government has implemented various measures and initiatives. Two key aspects have been the enactment of legislation that specifically addresses cyberbullying and the close collaboration with various institutions to raise awareness about cyberbullying, promote digital literacy, and provide training to deal with this type of situation. We can also see the existence of prevention campaigns and appeals to report cases of cyberbullying to the authorities or trusted adults.**

Furthermore, **adults are one of the main target audiences of training activities**, initiatives and campaigns, recognizing the importance of making adults aware of the dangers of aggressive online behaviour to reach and to raising awareness among younger audiences. In this sense, it is also relevant to highlight that collaborative initiatives have been launched to develop innovative tools and resources that help identify and **prevent cyberbullying incidents**. These **efforts** include the creation of **dedicated helplines and online reporting systems**, such as the ones promoted by INCIDE, enabling victims of all ages to seek support and report cyberbullying and other aggressive or violent situations.

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6. United Kingdom: NGOs and Legislation Frameworks

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6.1. Statistical data

Over the past half-decade, research has shed light on the intricate landscape of social media engagement among preadolescents and adolescents in the United Kingdom. A study conducted by Ofcom in 2020 revealed that approximately 71% of 12–15-year-olds have social media accounts, a notable rise from 45% in 2010. The report also highlighted that Snapchat, Instagram, and TikTok emerged as the preferred platforms, with these young users spending an average of 3 hours per day online, often accessing social media through smartphones (Ofcom, 2020).

More recent research from Ofcom shows that almost all children aged 3-17 went online (97%) in 2022, either at home or elsewhere, with the figure only slightly lower for 3-4-year-olds (87%) (Ofcom, 2023). Moreover, a third of children aged between 8 and 17 with a social media profile have an adult “user age” after signing up with a false date of birth, according to Yonder Consulting, who conducted research commissioned by Ofcom in 2022 (Ofcom, 2022).

6.2. National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

Qualitative insights from focus groups conducted by the [NSPCC in 2019](#) have brought to the forefront the issue of cyberbullying, a growing concern among young social media users. Participants recounted instances of online harassment, peer pressure, and body image anxieties stemming from interactions on these platforms (NSPCC, 2019).

A collaborative study between the Universities of Birmingham and Manchester in 2022 found that excessive social media use was associated with increased feelings of loneliness and depression among adolescents.

While these platforms offer avenues for self-expression and community building, the data highlights the need for comprehensive strategies to address the challenges posed by social media use and misuse. Initiatives such as the UK Safer Internet Centre have been working to promote digital literacy, online safety, and responsible social media usage among young users.

Some of the available secondary data from national research regarding various aspects of social media use among preadolescents in the UK show the following:

- **Social Media Penetration:** Reports from sources like Ofcom (the UK's communications regulator) have indicated a steady rise in social media usage among preadolescents (children aged 9-12) (see Ofcom, 2020; 2022; 2023).
- **Preferred Platforms:** Instagram, Snapchat, and TikTok have been among the most popular social media platforms for preadolescents. These platforms are often chosen due to their visual and interactive nature, catering to the preferences of younger users.
- **Time Spent:** Research from the Royal Society for Public Health (RSPH, 2017) and the Young Health Movement (2018) found that young people in the UK, including preadolescents, were

spending an average of 3 hours per day on social media. This prolonged screen time has raised concerns about potential impacts on mental health and overall well-being.

- **Digital Literacy and Parental Involvement:** Research by organizations like Childnet International has shown that while preadolescents are becoming more digitally savvy, there is still a need for increased digital literacy education. Moreover, parents' active involvement in guiding their children's online activities has been identified as crucial for ensuring safe and responsible social media use (see Childnet.com).
- **Privacy and Data Protection:** The issue of data privacy has also emerged as a concern, with preadolescents potentially sharing personal information without fully understanding the implications. Research from the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) has highlighted the importance of educating young users about protecting their privacy online (ICO, 2021).

6.3. Good practice examples (national and NGOs)

The phenomenon of social media use and misuse in schools and other contexts is a growing concern in the UK, with the potential risk also for cyberbullying, online harassment, addiction and other negative effects. Here are some leading organisations and good-practice examples in addressing these issues.

The UK Safer Internet Centre

The UK Safer Internet Centre is a partnership of three leading organisations: Childnet International, Internet Watch Foundation (IWF) and the South West Grid for Learning (SWGfL). The Centre is co-funded by the European Commission's Connecting Europe Facility and the UK government, and its main purpose is to promote the safe and responsible use of the internet and technology among children and young people.

The Centre provides resources, training, and advice to educators, parents, and young people on how to stay safe online. They offer guidance on **how to manage social media use in schools** and have developed a range of **teaching resources on digital citizenship**. The Centre also coordinates **Safer Internet Day in the UK**, which is a global campaign aimed at promoting the safe and responsible use of technology and raising awareness of online safety issues. Safer Internet Day is celebrated annually on the second Tuesday of February and brings together a range of stakeholders from across the UK and globally to discuss online safety issues and promote positive use of digital technology.

Link to the UK Safer Internet Centre: <https://saferinternet.org.uk/>

The Digital Schools Awards

The Digital Schools Awards is a national programme. It is run by Digital Schools Awards Ltd, a **not-for-profit organisation** that was set up in 2015 by HP, Hewlett Packard Enterprise, Intel, and Microsoft. The programme is supported by a range of other organisations, including Education Scotland, Jisc, and the Scottish Government.

The Digital Schools Awards program is designed to help schools develop a comprehensive **digital skill strategy that includes the use of social media**. The program provides a framework for schools to **assess their digital skills** and provides support and **guidance on how to develop these skills further**. Schools can work towards achieving one of three levels of accreditation: Digital School Award, Digital School Award+, and Digital School Award and Excellence in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering

and Mathematics). By recognizing and celebrating schools that are doing this well, the program helps to promote best practices in digital education and support the continued development of digital skills among young people in the UK.

Link to the Digital Schools Awards website: <https://www.digitalschoolsawards.co.uk/>

The Social Media Code of Conduct for Schools

This code of conduct was developed by the **UK Council for Child Internet Safety** (UKCCIS) and outlines guidelines for the **appropriate use of social media** by schools, staff, and pupils. It includes advice on privacy settings, acceptable content, and how to handle cyberbullying. Overall, the Code of Conduct for Schools is a valuable resource for schools in the UK, providing them with practical advice and best practices for navigating the use of social media platforms.

Link to the guide developed by UKCCIS:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/online-safety-in-schools-and-colleges-questions-from-the-governing-board>

UK Council for Child Internet Safety

The UK Council for Child Internet Safety (UKCCIS) is a group of over 200 organisations that work together **to promote the safe and responsible use of the internet** among children and young people in the UK. UKCCIS was established in 2008, and it brings together a range of stakeholders, including government departments, industry players, and non-governmental organisations. The aim of UKCCIS is to provide **a collaborative forum for organisations to work together to promote online safety** for children and young people. It provides a platform for organisations to share information, best practices, and resources and to coordinate their efforts to raise awareness of online safety issues.

Link to the UKCCIS website: <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/uk-council-for-internet-safety>

The #DITTO Magazine (newsletter)

The #DITTO Magazine is a **free online magazine and newsletter** that provides updates on the latest trends and issues in online safety. It is aimed at educators, parents, and young people and provides practical advice on how to stay safe online, including tips on social media use. The newsletter is produced by the (award-winning) online safety organisation, **Alan Mackenzie Ltd**.

#DITTO covers **a range of online safety topics**, including social media, online gaming, cyberbullying, and online grooming. The magazine also includes reviews of online safety resources, updates on new technology trends, and advice on how to stay up-to-date with the latest online safety issues. It can be downloaded from the [#DITTO website](#). The latest issues of #DITTO magazine was published in 2021.

The Digital Citizenship Programme

This programme, developed by **Childnet International**, provides a range of resources and training for educators on how to promote digital citizenship in schools. The programme includes guidance on **how to use social media positively and safely**, as well as how to handle cyberbullying and other online risks.

Childnet International is a member of the **UK Safer Internet Centre**, and it works in partnership with a range of other organisations to promote online safety for children and young people.

Link to the Digital Citizenship Programme: <https://www.childnet.com/resources/know-it-all-secondary-toolkits/lower-secondary-toolkit/digital-citizenship/>

6.4. UK legislation and regulation

On 12 May 2021, the UK government introduced the Online Safety Bill. The bill aims to establish a new regulatory regime to address illegal and harmful content online including online disinformation, terrorist propaganda and pro-suicide content, providing for fines and other penalties for non-compliance. The draft imposes a duty of legal care on online service providers to protect their users by imposing an obligation on them to moderate user-generated content to prevent other users from being exposed to illegal and/or harmful content and material.

The Bill at this moment (March 2023) is at the Committee stage in the House of Lords. Committee stage involves detailed line by line examination of the separate parts (clauses and schedules) of a Bill.

During committee stage every clause of the Bill must be agreed to and votes on any amendments can take place. All suggested amendments must be considered, if a member wishes, and members can discuss an issue for as long as they want.

This Law aims to protect citizens from harmful or offensive content online. The proposal includes some measures to protect minors. For example, the obligation for technology companies to implement measures to prevent the dissemination of content harmful to minors, such as violence, child pornography and human trafficking. The independent online safety authority will have the power to impose fines on tech companies that fail to comply with the rules. The Bill also includes measures to ensure transparency and accountability of technology companies.

6.5. European Union legislation and regulation

The European Union has implemented several regulations that are relevant to social media frameworks and companies operating within the EU.

One of the most significant regulations is the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**, which came into effect in May 2018. It mandates that companies must obtain explicit consent from users before collecting or processing their personal data, and provides individuals with the right to access, rectify, and erase their personal data. Failure to comply with GDPR can result in significant fines and reputational damage.

Regarding minors (under the age of 18) as data subjects, GDPR sets a general age of consent at 16, meaning that processing the data of a subject younger than 15 is prohibited by law. For circumstances in which data concerning children under the age of 16 is processed, such processing must be carried out with the permission of their parent or legal guardian. Processing this data without adult consent contravenes EU law. It is worth noting that the GDPR's recommended age of consent of 16 is not mandatory. According to Article 8 (1), member states may establish laws that lower the age of consent to 13, but not below.

Another important regulation is the **e-Commerce Directive**, which provides guidelines for the liability of online intermediaries for third-party content. Social media platforms are considered intermediaries under this directive and can be held liable for hosting illegal content.

The Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD) is another relevant regulation that imposes rules on audiovisual media services, including video-sharing platforms. It requires such platforms to implement measures to protect minors from harmful content and to ensure that advertising is transparent and does not contain any hidden messages.

The Audiovisual Media Services Directive's general approach of a system of graduated regulation also applies to the protection of minors. The less control a viewer has, and the more harmful specific content could be, the more restrictions apply. The rules in this Directive are supplemented by the [1998 Recommendation](#) and [2006 Recommendation](#) on the protection of minors and human dignity. The AVMSD considers that the protection of minors has to always be balanced with other important values of a democratic society like freedom of expression and cannot work without parental responsibility. The Commission has also published a [specific communication on video games](#).

The **Network and Information Systems Directive** (NIS Directive) aims to improve the security of network and information systems across the EU. It requires companies operating in critical sectors, including social media platforms, to take measures to prevent and handle cybersecurity incidents.

Finally, the **Digital Services Act** (DSA) is a proposed regulation by the European Union that will apply to online platforms, including social media platforms, starting in 2024. The DSA aims to modernise the regulatory framework for digital services, increase transparency and accountability, and promote innovation while ensuring the protection of users' fundamental rights.

The Digital Services Act aims to further regulate the activities of online platforms, including social media. This act places greater responsibilities on owner companies forcing them to create plans to remove illegal content and comply with stricter reporting, regulatory cooperation and risk management protocols.

Its provisions encompass preventing social media sites from profiling children for ads, granting users the ability to challenge content removal, verifying authenticity of products sold on online marketplaces (e.g. Amazon), and combating threats such as disinformation and cyber-violence towards women. Infractions of the act carry the possibility of incurring a fine equivalent to 6% of a company's worldwide revenue and, in the most severe circumstances, result in a temporary suspension of the platform. The EU may also impose a requirement for immediate remedial action to resolve any issues. Consumers will have the right to seek reimbursement for any harm incurred because of a violation of the regulation. The most promising aspects of the law are the rules that govern platforms' relationships with users. Notably, platforms will have to disclose information about the algorithms that influence what content is recommended to users and give users the option to turn off these recommendation systems.

6.6. International organisations (United Nations)

The United Nations Organization has developed a set of binding conventions, which derive from the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948. The protection of minors in the online environment also originates from conventions that protect human rights.

In the hyper-digitalised scenario in which we live, it is interesting to note how the United Nations calls both the public and private individuals to responsibility and co-responsibility regarding the right to the protection of minors in the digital environment. In **the Guidelines of the United Nations Committee for the Rights of the Child**, specifically in General Comment No. 20 of 2016, it is stated that: «The digital environment can expose adolescents to risks [...]. However, this should not limit adolescents' access to the digital environment. Their safety should be promoted through holistic strategies, including digital literacy regarding online risks and strategies to keep them safe, strengthening legislation and law enforcement mechanisms to tackle online abuse and fight impunity, and the training of parents and professionals who work with children [...]».

In the context of UN regulation, **the 2020 ITU Guidelines on the Protection of Children Online** (Geneva, 23 June 2020) are also relevant. The International Telecommunication Union has issued new Guidelines on the Protection of Children Online, a set of recommendations for children, parents and educators, industry and policy makers on how to contribute to the development of a safe and responsible online environment for children and young people. This new edition of the guidelines also addresses important shortcomings of the previous editions: among these the one relating to the situation of children with disabilities and the one relating to the specific needs of other vulnerable social groups, for whom the online world could represent a particularly important opportunity for a full social participation.

Some countries have established specific regulations relating to the field of prevention activities against the dangers and risks associated with the use of the web by minors, also resulting in the sanctions for those who break the provisions, and other countries in which the issues are included in the penal system already in place. In Europe, France adopted in 2020 a law for the protection of minors on social media, approved unanimously by the National Assembly. The aim of the law is to regulate the exploitation of the image of children under 16 on online platforms, thus setting an important precedent in the field of kid influencer marketing. Due to these provisions, the minor can personally exercise the right to be forgotten, also due to the obligation of the platforms to quickly remove the contents subject of the request.

6.7. Conclusions

In summary, in UK there are several good practice examples in the UK for addressing the phenomenon of social media in schools and other contexts. These examples include resources and training from organisations like the UK Safer Internet Centre and Childnet International, codes of conduct for schools, and digital skills assessment programmes like the Digital Schools Awards.

Some of the common traits of these interventions:

- Developing age-appropriate materials,
- Encouraging open communication,
- Providing training and support for teachers,
- Using peer-to-peer education,
- Promoting positive online behaviour (e.g. empathy and kindness online),

These initiatives all aim to **promote safe and responsible social media use, beyond the cyberbullying etiquette**, and help to mitigate the negative effects in all spheres of life of young people.

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Conclusions

The conclusions from the desk research in non-partner countries aim to provide additional or distinct insights compared to those identified in the five partner countries. Key takeaways are summarised below:

1. High policy and institutional investment in digital safety

Countries like Australia, the UK, and Finland have developed dedicated agencies, robust national strategies, and legal instruments to address online safety (e.g., Australia's eSafety Commissioner, UK's Online Safety Bill, Finland's national digital curriculum). These efforts illustrate institutional readiness and structured policy responses.

2. Emphasis on mental health and well-being

Research from Australia, Spain and the UK establishes clear links between excessive social media use and mental health risks such as anxiety, loneliness, and depression—particularly among preadolescent girls.

3. Gender-specific risks and content exposure

Data from Belgium, Spain and Finland highlight that girls are more exposed to harmful content (e.g., self-harm, body image ideals, hate speech) and suffer greater emotional distress online.

4. Decentralized media literacy implementation

In Rhode Island and Spain, despite legislative intent, media literacy remains inconsistently implemented—depending heavily on local educators or external organisations. This highlights a structural challenge: the gap between national policy and local practice, particularly evident in U.S. contexts. By contrast, the Belgian case illustrates a decentralised governance model in which media education is primarily developed at Community level, resulting in differentiated but complementary approaches rather than a uniform national framework.

5. Early exposure and misleading age use

Findings from the UK and Australia show that children join social media platforms earlier than allowed, often by misrepresenting their age. This creates scenarios where preadolescents navigate adult digital spaces without appropriate safeguards.

DESK RESEARCH

This report is part of the Erasmus+ project ASAP – *A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education*.

It presents the transdisciplinary knowledge contributions prepared by project partners. In addition, the report summarises the key findings of partner countries desk research reports as well as the key findings of the other countries desk research report. In the end, the report provides implications for the ASAP project, based on the findings of conducted desk research.

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